

SOLUTION SET 1

- Mechanical ventilation through a decentralized ventilation system
- Space heating and cooling through a centralized heat pump with water storage
- Air movement through ceiling fan

LOW-RISE BUILDING

3 floors, 7 dwellings of 80-110m² each

MEDITERRANEAN GEO-CLUSTER

ENERGY, LOAD MATCHING AND GRID INTERACTION

Self-generation
Self-consumption

Primary energy

Final energy

LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

Global Warming Potential (GWP)

Dynamic GWP

Thermal comfort
Relative Humidity comfort

ECONOMIC IMPACT

Overall cost

Investment cost

THE RESIDENTS' VOICES

Conflicting practices

NEED

Ventilating and being in contact with the outdoor space

RESPONSE

Opening windows. Very little use of the ventilation system

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HIGH-RISE BUILDING

8 floors, 20 dwellings of 50-75m² each

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INDOOR COMFORT

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Conflicting practices

NEED

Sleeping comfortably with an adequate temperature

RESPONSE

Turning off the heating system and opening windows

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Conflicting practices

NEED

Relaxing in the outdoor balcony (all year round) and being in contact with outdoor space

RESPONSE

Using an electric heater on the balcony

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Conflicting practices

NEED

Sleeping comfortably with an adequate temperature

RESPONSE

Turning off the heating, opening windows, changing dressing habits

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NEED

Ventilating and being in contact with the outdoor space

RESPONSE
Opening windows

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NEED

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RESPONSE

Cooling - having a fan always on to feel good

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NEED

Feeling cold/Missing a direct warmth source (fireplace)

RESPONSE

Adding an extra electric radiator

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NEED

Being in contact with outdoor space

RESPONSE

Opening windows, which interferes with the heating system and mechanical ventilation

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SOLUTION SET 2

- Mechanical ventilation through a decentralized system
- Space heating, cooling and DHW through a decentralized PHP
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NEED

Taking care of a loved one

RESPONSE

Extra heating by raising the temperature setpoint or adding an electric heater

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NEED
Getting rid of cleaning odours

RESPONSE
Opening windows instead of using mechanical ventilation

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NEED

Pleasing visitors when hosting at home

RESPONSE

Adjusting temperature to the visitors' thermal comfort expectations

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NEED

Getting rid of cooking smells

RESPONSE

Using both mechanical ventilation and natural ventilation (creating a draught)

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NEED

Taking care of a loved one with special health needs

RESPONSE

Extra heating by adding an electric heater

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NEED
Ventilating while having health issues (asthma, allergies)

RESPONSE
Opening windows for a short time

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NEED

Working easier with residents that have special needs

RESPONSE

Leaving apartment main doors open, which jeopardizes mechanical ventilation

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RESPONSE

Opening windows (having "cracked open" windows) & having appropriate duvets

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